

SLiCE: An Open Data Model for Scalable High-Definition Life Cycle Engineering, Hotspot Analysis and Dynamic Assessment of Buildings.

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Abstract

Building construction and operation are responsible for around 40% of global energy-related greenhouse gas emissions. To identify emissions reduction and removal potentials as well as wider environmental impacts, researchers, policy, and decision makers need comprehensive life cycle sustainability assessment insights on individual buildings and building stocks at large.

This article proposes a data model for scalable, high-definition life cycle analysis of building – the SLiCE data model – as a promising solution to overcome the limitations identified for existing models. The article conceptualizes the problem within the Space-Time-Indicator Nexus; presents the proposed SLiCE data structure; and showcases practical uses of SLiCE data for environmental hotspot analysis as well as for dynamic assessment of climate impacts.

The open SLiCE data model and SLiCE hotspot analysis tool are henceforth available for implementation within life cycle assessment of building and building stocks, enabling comprehensive insights on buildings' environmental impacts across spatiotemporal scales.

Keywords

Data models; Life Cycle Assessment; Environmental Engineering; Data Science; Whole Life Carbon; Buildings and Construction; Building Stock Modelling

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Software and data availability

The SLiCE building data model as well as the presented implementation in the SLiCE hotspot analysis prototype are open source and available with this article. The SLiCE hotspot analysis, implemented as an IPython Jupyter Notebook with interactive widgets, tool is available on Github (https://github.com/mroeck/slice_hotspots/), with the submission pre-release published via Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/645859866>). All items are published under a GNU General Public License v3.0. We encourage you to review, reuse, and refine the model and scripts and share-alike.

Author contributions

Martin Röck: Conceptualization; methodology; data curation and visualization; writing (original draft, review and editing); project administration. **Alexander Passer:** Methodology; writing (review and editing); supervision. **Karen Allacker:** Methodology; writing (review and editing); supervision.

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1. Introduction

The construction and operation of buildings is responsible for almost 40% of global energy-related greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. In light of the accelerating climate and environmental emergency, policy and decision makers across the world are urged to step up decarbonization efforts to ensure an adequate response. The European Union (EU) is seen as a pioneer in systematic decarbonization efforts, aiming to link up various policy initiatives to drive decarbonization across different sectors, including for building construction and operation [1–4]. However, to avoid ‘carbon tunnel vision’ when defining targets, policies, or strategies it is crucial to identify and resolve potential ‘burden-shifting’ to other impact categories or life cycle stages through a comprehensive life cycle-based sustainability assessment (LCSA). LCSA approaches have therefore become a fundamental tool in the EU policy making toolbox [5,6] to model and understand the wider environmental, social and economic implications of potential decisions. Insights from life cycle modelling of buildings and building stocks are fundamental to achieving the anticipated decline of emissions towards net-zero by mid-century [6–8]. To make informed decisions in context of buildings, decision makers need comprehensive insights on buildings’ environmental impacts across spatiotemporal scales, meaning insights on the distribution of environmental impacts across different spatial elements of buildings as well as across different stages of the building life cycle. However, despite this clear need, models and tools available thus far are limited by lack of data granularity and model resolution in building analysis when applied at higher (macro-)scale levels [6,9] (See Figure 1).

Figure 1: Prevailing trade-off between policy-relevance and data granularity and model resolution across spatial levels

(Own figure, adapted from [10])

To adequately assess environmental impacts and avoid burden-shifting across spatial and temporal scales, it is hence fundamental to advance data granularity of building level life cycle information. High granularity data inputs are fundamental to enabling improved model resolution and the inclusion of all relevant environmental impact categories and analysis of environmental hotspots at higher scale levels, such as for building stock modelling.

An appropriate logic and protocol for systematic hotspot analysis has been proposed by [11] as part of the environmental footprint (EF) initiative for assessment both product environmental footprints (PEF) as well as organization environmental footprints (OEF). Systematic screening and analysis of environmental hotspots, as proposed by [11], means assessing in a clear and reproducible way the most relevant aspects of a product’s environmental footprint (EF) with regards to its most relevant indicators, most relevant life cycle stages, most relevant processes as well as most relevant elementary flows – as shown in Figure 2. Each of these perspectives is important and relevant for diverse sets of stakeholders, for example: to identify and avoid environmental trade-offs (most relevant indicators and most relevant life cycle stages); to inform building and construction professionals or construction product manufacturers about hotspots within their building or product (most relevant life cycle stages, most relevant processes, most relevant elementary flows); as well as to inform policy makers, data and documentation requirements for monitoring and guiding sustainable development of buildings and building stocks (most relevant processes, most relevant elementary flows). Application of the hotspot analysis protocol to buildings has been showcased within the PEF4Buildings project on testing the application of PEF to new buildings [12–14].

Figure 2: Concept of hotspot analysis for identification of most important aspects relevant for guiding green transition of buildings and construction across Europe (adapted from [11,12]).

However, while proven applicable in principle, there is still a lack of scalable solutions for enabling the wide implementation of such hotspot analyses for buildings in both policy research as well as industry practice[15,16]. This lack of scalable solutions for environmental hotspot analysis of buildings is linked to the lack of open data models for providing building related life cycle information with high granularity, especially regarding life cycle inventory (LCI) data and life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) results.

The objective of this article is to present the SLiCE data model, an accessible and open building data model aimed at researchers and industry professionals as well as policy experts, as a basis for implementing systematic screening and analysis of environmental hotspots in building research as well as, eventually, in everyday industry practice. This article presents the conceptualization of the problem within the Space-Time-Indicator Nexus and proposes the SLiCE data model as a potential solution. The added value of SLiCE is validated based on two main use cases of SLiCE data: a) a systematic analysis of environmental hotspots, via a custom-built hotspot analysis tool; and b) a dynamic assessment of climate impacts and carbon uptake, based on SLiCE data of bio-based building elements.

The SLiCE data model and related applications aim to offer open interfaces for researchers and industry professionals for joint elaboration and development, including for links to other models and use cases to advance together towards scalable, high-definition LCA of buildings and building stocks at scale.

2. Methods

2.1. High-definition life cycle information

2.1.1. Space-Time-Indicator (STI) framework

Life-cycle related information on buildings is interwoven in spatial and temporal dimensions and linked through various environmental, social, and economic indicators. This section aims at conceptualizing this nexus of multidimensional interrelations of life cycle information to clarify what information and granularity is available and/or required for different applications and use cases, taking systematic environmental hotspot analysis as an exemplary use case and proof-of-concept.

The Space-Time-Indicator (STI) framework (Figure 3) aims at providing such a conceptual framework and is based on three main dimensions of building life cycle-related information: Space; Time; and Indicators. For all dimensions, a notion of high or low ‘resolution’ is applied to express the granularity and level of definition in modelling and results provision for spatial and temporal information, as well as the comprehensiveness of indicators investigated in a particular analysis. In the present example, the spatial resolution focuses on the analysis of a building for which results can be provided as the sum at building level (level 0); per building element (level -1); per sub-element (work sections, components) (level -2); or per building material (level -3). Higher as well as lower scale levels can be added to this concept, such as the contribution of even smaller entities, such as raw materials, or the aggregation of results for different building clusters (e.g., a national building stock). In terms of temporal resolution, the results of building LCA are often provided as the sum across the whole life cycle (WLC) (A). In the European context, studies usually follow the related standard EN 15978, which suggests the modelling and reporting of results per life cycle stage (LCS) or life cycle module (LCM). Beyond the reporting of life cycle information in predefined categories, the actual point in time for the occurrence of something like GHG emissions, is of interest. The point in time can be specified along various resolutions, such as categorically per LCS, LCM or more specifically, per its year, month, or day of occurrence, and so on. Enabling the reporting of indicators/impacts on a yearly (or in future quarterly or monthly) basis will be useful and important for corporate Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) reporting. Looking to building energy modelling, and the emerging role of digital building logbooks, we can further anticipate that both energy- and material-related indicators will become available at daily, or in the case of energy, even hourly resolutions. These and other combinations of spatial and temporal resolution can be applied during life cycle analyses and used for reporting on the third dimension, indicators.

The STI framework and the life cycle modelling approach presented here are inspired by computational logics applied in Earth and environmental systems modelling [17,18] and geospatial analysis such as the space-time-attribute (STA) concept [19,20], data cubes and array programming more generally [21,22]. Inspired also by the struggle towards the application of standardised multi-dimensional data cubes in these domains, the STI framework, and the consecutive proposal of the SLiCE building data

model, aim at providing a step towards enabling the development and use of standardised data formats for analysis of life cycle related information based on: bins (i.e., analysis of results for a specific spatial item, at a specific time and for a specific indicators); bin time series (i.e., analysis of a spatial item and indicator(s) across time); time slices (i.e., analysis of results at a specific time regarding the contribution of different spatial items and indicators at that time); or combinations thereof.

Figure 3: Space-Time-Indicator (STI) framework depicting different spatial and temporal resolutions for life cycle related information, such as life cycle inventory data, environmental and other indicators.

2.1.2. Scalable data structures

The following paragraphs provide the background of the data structure logic utilised by the SLiCE data model and the software modules utilised for the implementation presented. The implementation of the SLiCE relies on IPython in Jupyter Notebook [23] and a variety of modules to support computation

[24], visualization and interactive presentation of the analysis [25]. A useful concept utilised in this context (e.g., HoloViz HoloViews [26]) is the distinction of variables/attributes into ‘key’ and ‘value’ dimensions. In this logic, *key dimensions*, refer to indexing dimensions or independent variables/attributes, and *value dimensions* refer to resulting data or dependent variables/attributes. This logic of key and value dimensions is henceforth applied to support explanation of the SLiCE data model.

'Wide'					vs.	'Tall'			
Index	Building	Material A - GWP	Material B - GWP	Material C - GWP		Index	Building	Material	GWP
0	A	300 kgCO2e	430 kgCO2e	450 kgCO2e		0	A	A	300 kgCO2e
1	B	200 kgCO2e	238 kgCO2e	-		1	A	B	430 kgCO2e
2	C	400 kgCO2e	-	600 kgCO2e		2	A	C	450 kgCO2e
						3	B	A	200 kgCO2e
						4	B	B	238 kgCO2e
						5	C	A	400 kgCO2e
						6	C	C	600 kgCO2e

Figure 4: Illustrative example of ‘wide’ and ‘tall’ data structures, both used within the SLiCE data model.

The SLiCE building data model deploys a blend of ‘tall’ and ‘wide’ data logic as a basis for the analysis of hotspots across spatiotemporal scales and other implementations. Figure 4 illustrates the difference of ‘wide’ and ‘tall’ data structures by giving an example of either logic in context of building life cycle information, specifically on the GWP for different materials (A-C) contained in different building cases (A-C). The example illustrates how a ‘wide’ data structure can offer the benefit of presenting building related information in a clear and more human-readable logic of ‘one line (row) per case’. However, with the downside of requiring empty fields where a certain attribute (column) is not applicable, thereby causing inefficiency in data storing and unnecessary computational burden during processing. On the other hand, a ‘tall’ data structure requires multiple rows to express the information per building, using attributes for the relevant dimensions ‘Material’ and ‘GWP’ and expressing the information on each separately. This data structure might be less intuitive at first, but allows to specify complex, multi-level information, for example on hierarchical life cycle inventory data and the related indicators. Furthermore, wide data structures can be challenging with regards to distinguishing value information on different granularity levels, such as the GWP at building level as well as at individual material levels. Tall data structures, as illustrated, store information on the finest granularity level available and can

then utilise a dynamic aggregation at requested level(s) using readily available computational operations such as Pandas ‘groupby’, for example. Tall data structures can therefore be considered particularly suitable for storing large amounts of data on strongly diversified items, such as life cycle information on buildings including on material composition, life cycle inventory, and indicators results.

Practical examples of ‘wide’ data structures in the building context are the data collection template (DCT) of [27–29] and the related building datasets presented in [28,30]. Practical examples for ‘tall’ data structures are the hierarchical, multi-level life cycle inventories developed in the context of BIM-based LCA as deployed in the PEF4Buildings project [13]. Suitable building life cycle information can be aligned with the SLiCE data model by transformation of selected attributes between ‘wide’ and ‘tall’ data, for example using Pandas ‘melt’ / ‘pivot’ [24,31,32].

2.2. Hotspots analysis protocol

The basis for the environmental hotspot analysis routine and prototype implementation presented here are the EF hotspot analysis protocol developed by [11] and experiences from its application within the PEF4Buildings project [12–14]. A summary of the hotspot analysis methodology [11] and specificities of this implementation is offered in Table 1 and elaborated in the following. In this implementation, the hotspot analysis protocol follows a three-step procedure, which involves identifying the most relevant indicators (e.g., impact categories), temporal hotspots (e.g., life cycle stages), and spatial hotspots (e.g., materials, processes and/or elementary flows):

1. **Most relevant indicators:** The first step is to identify environmental hotspots based on the most relevant impact categories, which are identified based on the normalised and weighted results. A default list of impact categories has been defined in context of PEF/OEF. However, the method allows adaptation to custom use cases, including a custom list of impact categories and related normalization and weighting factors.

The hotspot analysis script presented in this article considers: at least three relevant impact categories (where applicable); the most relevant impact categories as all impact categories that cumulatively contribute to at least 80% of the total impact by default, with a variable threshold value, starting from the largest to the smallest contributions. Computation of the percentage

contribution of any process or flow is assessed based on absolute values (i.e., the minus sign is ignored) to account for the relevance of any indicator value, even if negative. The presented prototype hotspots tool is flexible with regards to processing assessment results with different impact categories and related custom weighting sets.

2. Temporal hotspots: The second step is to identify temporal hotspots, based on the most relevant life cycle stages. The original method suggests considering all life cycle stages (LCS) that contribute over 80% (before normalisation and weighting) to any of the impact categories. The default life cycle stages should be raw material acquisition and pre-processing, production of the main product, product distribution and storage, use stage scenario (if in scope), and end-of-life (including product/part reuse, recovery/recycling; if in scope).

This implementation identifies the most relevant life cycle stages based on the normalised and weighted results, in line with the application of the method in the PEF4Buildings study. The most relevant life cycle stages are those which together contribute to at least 80% of any of the most relevant impact categories identified. The current implementation thereby diverts from the original PEF/OEF guidance, which suggests identification of most relevant LCS based on characterised results for each indicators, rather than overall weighted results. It is, however, possible to adapt the script accordingly and utilise equal weighting for individual steps of the analysis in the future. Furthermore, this implementation is based on the life cycle model of building LCA as defined in EN 15978 and supports analysis of cradle to grave life cycle results.

3. Spatial hotspots: The third step is to identify the spatial hotspots, which can be identified at different levels of granularity, such as most relevant processes (or elementary flows), the so-called 'level-1'. In this implementation, the level for contribution analysis can be customised to define whether as building element (level-1), building sub-elements (e.g., work sections) (level-2), material level (level-3), or any other lower level available in the dataset. Most relevant spatial items (level-1) are then identified for each of the most relevant impact categories identified and for each life cycle stage, with an indication of the most relevant ones. Furthermore, the definition of 'hotspots' by [11] in context of PEF/OEF is: A) Life cycle stages, processes, and elementary flows cumulatively contributing at least 50% to any impact category

before normalisation and weighting (from the most contributing in descending order), or B) At least the two most relevant life cycle stages, processes, and at least two elementary flows (minimum 6), with the option to identify additional hotspots.

This implementation offers the possibility to individually select (include or exclude) indicators, temporal items (e.g., life cycle stages), and spatial items (e.g., materials), as appropriate for a particular study. This also allows to follow the methodology in the PEF4Buildings study, where the levels for which most relevant processes are to be identified are distinguished based on the contribution of the operational stage to life cycle impacts (if >50%, both use stage and whole life cycle excluding use stage are assessed separately).

Table 1: Summary of the hotspot analysis method deployed in this implementation.

Most relevant items	Identification of relevance	Threshold
Indicators (e.g., impact categories)	Based on normalised and weighted results, ideally from a comprehensive set of indicators (e.g., LCA). Options: Using predefined sets or 'equal weighting' (e.g., for already normalised values); Selection of only one or more indicators (e.g., limit to GWP).	The indicators that cumulatively contribute to at least 80% of the total indicator value, by default. Customizable threshold value (0-100%), including option for 'no threshold' (100%).
Temporal items (e.g., life cycle stages) 'Temporal hotspots'	For each of the most relevant indicators (e.g., impact categories). Options: Equal weighting; Limited indicators selection.	All temporal items (e.g., life cycle stages, point in time) contributing cumulatively more than 80% to any indicator (e.g., impact category), by default. Customizable threshold value (0-100%).
Spatial items (e.g., building materials) 'Spatial hotspots'	For each indicator (e.g., impact category) and temporal item (e.g., life cycle stage), with indication of the most relevant ones. Option: Custom definition of 'level-1' if multi-dimensional data input available (e.g., SLiCE).	All spatial items (e.g., building materials) contributing cumulatively more than 80% to any indicator (e.g., impact category), by default. Customizable threshold value (0-100%).

2.3. Dynamic life cycle assessment

The use of SLiCE data for dynamic impact assessment was tested within [33], which serves as an input to the description of methods and materials described in the following.

Figure 5: Conceptual steps of SLiCE-based dynamic life cycle assessment. Starting from a SLiCE dataset with temporally explicit, dynamic foreground LCI on products and processes; multiplied by a static background LCI on elementary flows, e.g., from the Ecoinvent database v3.8 [34]; and temporally dynamic characterization factors, such as presented by Levasseur et al. [35]; are combined to achieve a SLiCE-based dynamic LCA.

The static LCA and dynamic LCA (DLCA) workflows were custom-built and programmed using Anaconda Jupyter Notebooks [36], iPython [23] and the Pandas package for data handling [24,37]. For the dynamic LCA, a dynamic LCI is computed considering emissions in the year they occur, based on the foreground inventory information provided in the respective SLiCE dataset and static background LCI from Ecoinvent [34]. The temporal resolution is one year. The dynamic foreground inventory is combined with a detailed background inventory from the LCA background database. The approach of a SLiCE-based dynamic impact assessment is tested based on the four most important GHGs: CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, CO.

2.3.1. Dynamic LCI foreground: Products and processes from SLiCE

As a basis for the SLiCE-based dynamic LCA, a SLiCE dataset with temporally explicit, dynamic foreground LCI on products and processes is required. This application requires a SLiCE dataset of a minimum temporal resolution ‘STI:D’, i.e., disaggregated information on life cycle processes by point in time (year). Furthermore, the spatial resolution of the dataset requires sufficient level of detail to determine the specific activities, products and processes, occurring in a given year. The latter is required

to allow a mapping of the foreground LCI with background data on elementary flows related to those activities. In the case of buildings or building elements, this means as SLiCE dataset with information on the specific material and/or energy flows taking place in any given year.

2.3.2. Static LCI background: Elementary flows from Ecoinvent

Furthermore, (static) background LCI is required to obtain information on elementary flows, such as flows of different GHGs. In this example, the LCA background database used is Ecoinvent version 3.8 [34]. Ecoinvent records related to the foreground products and processes were used to obtain detailed background inventory data on selected GHG emissions (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, CO), considering exchanges related to ‘fossil’, ‘from soil or biomass stock’, and ‘non-fossil’, respectively.

2.3.3. Dynamic LCIA: Dynamic characterization factors (CFs)

SLiCE foreground and Ecoinvent background LCI are then multiplied with dynamic characterization factors (CFs) to obtain the global warming impact of the building element as a function of time. By dividing the life cycle into yearly time steps, the dynamic inventory for each greenhouse gas (GHG) is obtained by summing the emissions occurring at each time step. This example applies SLiCE together with the dynamic impact assessment method of Levasseur et al. [35]. Levasseur et al. introduced a methodology that enables the calculation of the time-dependent impact on global warming (GWI) in a life cycle by incorporating dynamic characterization factors.

$$(1) \quad GWI(t) = \sum_i GWI_i(t) = \sum_i \sum_{j=0}^t [g_i]_j \times [DCF_i]_{t-j} \quad [35]$$

$$(2) \quad GWI(t) = \sum_i \sum_{j=0}^t [S_i]_j \times [B_i] \times [DCF_i]_{t-j} \quad (\text{Our approach})$$

As specified in equation (1) [35], the calculation of the GWI at a specific time (t) caused by the inventory (g) related to a particular GHG (i) involves multiplying the total emission (dynamic inventory result) at time (t) by the dynamic characterization factor (DCF) at time 0. Additionally, the GWI calculation includes adding the score assigned to the total emission at time (t-1) multiplied by the DCF at time 1, and so on, until finally incorporating the total emission at time 0 multiplied by the DCF at time (t). This calculation captures the increase in radiative forcing at time (t) resulting from discrete GHG emissions throughout the entire life cycle process. The time horizon in this example is 100 years.

The SLiCE-based dynamic LCA expands on this logic, as illustrated in equation (2), by distinguishing the inventory (g) into a dynamic, SLiCE-based foreground inventory (S) providing information on the primary activities occurring across the life cycle, and a static background inventory (B) providing details on biosphere flows (such as GHG emissions) related to the foreground activities.

Further details on the method applied are available in the related master thesis [33].

2.4. Case study building elements

For testing the hotspot analysis tool and the dynamic impact assessment workflow, respectively, SLiCE datasets have been generated from bio-based building elements presented in [38].

Building element BE figure + name	Work section						Material						
	WS name	Th [cm]	Freq B2.2	Freq B2.3	Freq B4.1	WS unit	Ecoinvent record	M unit	Ratio M/WS	ρ [kg/m³]	Mass [kg/m²]	λ [W/mK]	Scenario C1
EW01 (48.4 cm) Mass timber + hemp insulation	Cork finish	5.6	0	10	0	m²	Cork slab {RER} production Alloc Rec, U	m²	1	200	11.20	0.05	Waste wood
	Bituminised wood fibre board (screwed)	2.2	0	0	0	m²	Fibreboard, soft, bituminised [RER] production Alloc Rec, U	m²	1	253.59	5.58	0.05	Wood fibre board
							Chromium steel, screws [RER] production	pcs	5.56	7800	0.02		Wood fibre board
	Hemp insulation + structure	10	0	0	0	m²	Hemp insulation, packed [RER] production	m²	0.90	35	3.15	0.04	No C1 impact
							Softwood, untreated timber [BE] production, MIX	m²	0.10	400	4.00	0.12	No C1 impact
Thoma H100-W30	30.6	0	0	0	m²	Softwood, untreated prefabricated structural product [BE] production, MIX	m²	1	400	122.40	0.12	Waste wood	

Figure 6: Example of the input hierarchically modeled life cycle inventory by example of EW01 [38].

In their study, Mouton et al. focused on building elements and conducted various modeling and inventory activities. They defined multiple compositions for each building element type, incorporating bio-based construction techniques. The compositions were adjusted to achieve desired U-values or sound insulation. Variations of these elements were also defined by changing insulation materials. Additional compositions were derived from product catalogs and input from building stakeholders. The inventory modeling process involved categorizing input parameters and scenarios based on the respective levels (work section or material) in the Belgian MMG method [39–42]. Detailed compositions and hierarchically modeled LCIs of specific elements, such as the external wall EW01, were presented. The study utilized existing conventional element options from the MMG database. The

detailed inventory data and information on materials used in the respective life cycle inventories are available as supplementary information to that study and were used to generate SLiCE data for testing different use cases of SLiCE.

SLiCE data was generated for selected external wall (EW) elements to enable: showcasing a SLiCE dataset example (section 3.1) based on element 'EW05'; the environmental hotspot analysis tool (section 3.2) based on element 'EW05'; as well as the dynamic modelling of climate impacts and biogenic carbon uptake (section 3.3) based on EW 'MMG09'.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. SLiCE data model

3.1.1. Conceptual logic of the SLiCE data model

The SLiCE data model - illustrated in Figure 7 - deploys a combination of 'wide and 'tall' data structures. The data model logic represents key dimensions expressed in spatial and temporal attributes via a 'tall' data structure and combines it with value dimensions, indicator results, implemented as a 'wide' data structure to allow efficient expansion with further indicators.

The illustration in Figure 7 indicates that a variety of spatial attributes (key dimensions) can be accommodated within the data model, following a hierarchical building information modelling approach. Examples of hierarchical levels for such spatial information are the levels of building, element, sub-element (or work section), construction material (or construction product). Higher as well as lower scale spatial levels can be implemented as needed. As mentioned, spatial attributes are represented using a tall data structure. Similarly, temporal attributes (key dimensions) can be implemented at different levels of granularity, such as following EN 15978 and specifying the respective life cycle stages or module an activity occurs in. The example also anticipated the specification of 'nested' life cycle stages, where applicable. Nested modules can occur, for example, for processes related to replacement of building elements, which triggers both production (of the new element) and recycling or end-of-life (for the element being replaced). Furthermore, detailed temporal information on the 'point in time' a process occurs in can be accommodated within the SLiCE data model.

Spatial attributes (keys)					
Hierarchical building information modelling (element-method)					
[...]	Building	Element	Worksection	Construction material/product	[...]
-	Bldg A	Elem A	Wsec A	MatC A	-
-	Bldg A	Elem A	Wsec A	MatC B	-
-	Bldg A	Elem A	Wsec B	MatC A	-
-	Bldg A	Elem A	Wsec B	MatC C	-
-	Bldg A	Elem B	Wsec C	MatC D	-
-	Bldg A	Elem B	Wsec C	MatC E	-
-	Bldg A	Elem B	Wsec A	MatC A	-
-	Bldg A	Elem B	Wsec A	MatC B	-
-	[...]	[...]	[...]	[...]	-

Temporal attributes (keys)					
Building life cycle stages/modules and point in time					
[...]	Life cycle stage	Life cycle module	Nested module	Point in time (year)	[...]
-	A - Production	A1	-	0	-
-	A - Production	A2	-	0	-
-	A - Production	A3	-	0	-
-	B - Use phase	B6	-	1	-
-	B - Use phase	B6	-	2	-
-	B - Use phase	B6	-	3	-
-	B - Use phase	B4	A1	15	-
-	B - Use phase	B4	A2	15	-
-	B - Use phase	B4	A3	15	-
-	[...]	[...]	[...]	[...]	-

Indicator attributes (values)					
LCI amounts and LCIA results					
[...]	Material amount	Energy amount	Indicator GWP	Indicator PM	[...]
-	xx kg	-	xx kgCO2e	xx kgPM2,5e	-
-	-	yy kWh	yy kgCO2e	yy kgPM2,5e	-
-	zz kg	zz kWh	zz kgCO2e	zz kgPM2,5e	-
-	[...]	[...]	[...]	[...]	-

Figure 7: SLiCE data logic combining spatial attributes (keys), temporal attributes (keys) and indicator attributes (values) to accommodate scalable, high-definition life cycle information of buildings.

When, for example, implemented as the ‘year’ a process occurs, the point in time can give valuable context into the timing of environmental impacts to support identification of relevant phenomena such as the upfront embodied carbon spike of building material production (occurring in or even before year ‘0’) or the fact that operational emissions are spread out across the various years of a building life cycle.

Deploying the SLiCE data model with life cycle information specified by point in time (e.g., ‘year’) can furthermore enable the implementation of dynamic LCIA, based on changing characterization factors over time. Indicator attributes (value dimensions) are implemented using a ‘wide’ logic, as mentioned, meaning information is spread out horizontally rather than stacked vertically so that each indicator attribute is represented with an individual column. Note that stacking of (parts of) the indicator attributes can be appropriate, such as for attributes indicating material or energy flows, depending on the implementation and use case.

The SLiCE data model supports provision of high-granularity LCI and LCIA information, and as such can be combined with other relevant information on the building, the object of assessment – including its context and site variables, relevant building design parameters, relevant information on assessment methods, and more – using, for example, the list of attributes proposed in [30].

3.1.2. Practical example of a SLiCE dataset

Table 2 shows an example SLiCE dataset, generated from an implementation of the SLiCE data model in combination with KU Leuven’s MMG building LCA tool (‘MMG+_KULeuven’)[39–42] for the generation of LCA data on buildings across of buildings across scales. The sample dataset shows the element EW05. In full, it consists of approximately 200 rows representing various activities corresponding to the modeled life cycle of this element, spanning a duration of 60 years. The table provides an overview of a typical SLiCE dataset on building element level, showing various spatial attributes such as element, work section, product/process (activity), and techflow. It also includes temporal attributes such as life cycle stage, life cycle module, point in time (year), and activity type. Additionally, the table presents indicator results included in the SLiCE dataset, including LCI amount (techflow) and LCIA results based on LCA indicators such as GWP, PM, and EP. At the bottom of the table, the LCIA totals are displayed, confirming the consistency of the high-resolution SLiCE dataset with the results reported in the original study conducted by [38].

Table 2: SLiCE dataset example based on building element (‘EW05 CLT + str blown’) from [38]. The table shows different spatial attributes (element, work section, product/process (activity), and techflow), temporal levels (life cycle stage, life cycle module, point in time (year), and activity type), as well as indicator results (LCI amount (techflow), and LCIA results (by

example of LCA indicators GWP, PM, EP)). The LCIA totals at the bottom of the table confirm coherence of the high-resolution SLiCE dataset with the results reported in the original study of [38].

Spatial attributes (keys)				Temporal attributes (keys)				Indicator attributes (values)			
Element	Worksection	Product/Process	Techflow	Life cycle stage	Life cycle module	Point in time	Activity type	LCI amounts	LCIA results		
element_name	worksection_name	activity_name	techflow_name	LCS_name	LCM_code	activity_year	activity_type	techflow_amount	indicator_GWP	indicator_PM	indicator_EP
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Cork slab (RER) produ	A1-3; Product	A1-3	0	Material in	1.12E+01	1.58E+01	1.44E-02	9.87E-03
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Infrastruc	fibre board + bitumen	Fibreboard, soft, bitum	A1-3; Product	A1-3	0	Material in	5.58E+00	3.88E+00	2.40E-03	2.48E-03
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Infrastruc	screws	Chromium steel, screw	A1-3; Product	A1-3	0	Material in	1.88E-02	1.36E-01	1.97E-04	8.78E-05
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Thermal i	blow-in straw	Straw, stand-alone prof	A1-3; Product	A1-3	0	Material in	1.51E+01	1.58E+00	7.21E-04	5.43E-03
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Thermal i	timber grid	Softwood, untreated tir	A1-3; Product	A1-3	0	Material in	6.40E+00	1.94E+00	6.88E-03	1.77E-03
EW05 CLT + str blown	External wall - loadbearing Prir	cross laminated timber	CLT, cross laminated tir	A1-3; Product	A1-3	0	Material in	6.59E+01	2.95E+01	8.07E-02	2.62E-02
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Transport, freight, lorry	A4-5; Construc	A4	0	Transport to site	1.01E+00	8.73E-02	4.80E-05	4.71E-05
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Cork slab (RER) produ	A4-5; Construc	A5	0	Material loss	5.60E-01	7.89E-01	7.19E-04	4.93E-04
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Softwood, laths, dried	B1-4; Use stag	B2	10	Process	2.20E-03	2.66E-01	9.46E-04	2.44E-04
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Chromium steel, screw	B1-4; Use stag	B2	10	Process	2.50E-03	1.82E-02	2.63E-05	1.17E-05
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Softwood, laths, dried	B1-4; Use stag	B2	20	Process	2.20E-03	2.66E-01	9.46E-04	2.44E-04
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Chromium steel, screw	B1-4; Use stag	B2	20	Process	2.50E-03	1.82E-02	2.63E-05	1.17E-05
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Softwood, laths, dried	B1-4; Use stag	B2	30	Process	2.20E-03	2.66E-01	9.46E-04	2.44E-04
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Chromium steel, screw	B1-4; Use stag	B2	30	Process	2.50E-03	1.82E-02	2.63E-05	1.17E-05
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Softwood, laths, dried	B1-4; Use stag	B2	40	Process	2.20E-03	2.66E-01	9.46E-04	2.44E-04
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Chromium steel, screw	B1-4; Use stag	B2	40	Process	2.50E-03	1.82E-02	2.63E-05	1.17E-05
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Softwood, laths, dried	B1-4; Use stag	B2	50	Process	2.20E-03	2.66E-01	9.46E-04	2.44E-04
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Chromium steel, screw	B1-4; Use stag	B2	50	Process	2.50E-03	1.82E-02	2.63E-05	1.17E-05
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Transport, freight, lorry	C1-4; End of li	C2	60	Transport EOL	1.40E+00	2.28E-01	1.08E-04	1.20E-04
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Infrastruc	fibre board + bitumen	Transport, freight, lorry	C1-4; End of li	C2	60	Transport EOL	1.77E+02	1.14E-01	5.36E-05	6.00E-05
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Sorting of waste combu	C1-4; End of li	C3	60	Process	5.60E-01	9.06E-04	5.34E-07	7.04E-07
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Infrastruc	fibre board + bitumen	Sorting of waste wood	C1-4; End of li	C3	60	Process	4.24E+01	2.73E-04	2.39E-07	3.01E-07
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Incineration of waste w	C1-4; End of li	C4	60	Process	1.06E+01	1.02E-01	3.11E-04	5.87E-04
EW05 CLT + str blown	Wall - external finish Cladding	cork (32-80mm)	Sorting of waste combu	C1-4; End of li	C4	60	Process	1.06E+01	1.72E-02	1.01E-05	1.34E-05
								TOTAL	60.25	0.12	0.05

3.2. SLiCE-based hotspot analysis

The SLiCE hotspots tool enables the analysis of environmental hotspots within building assessment results following the SLiCE data model – see Figure 8 for a conceptual overview of the tool, based on snippets of the current prototype of the tool, implemented via JupyterNotebook [36] and Panel [25].

To start, the hotspot analysis script requires some user inputs and settings:

1. First, a SLiCE-compliant dataset as well as a file with weighting factors related to the impact indicators in the dataset have to be specified.
2. Second, the ‘level 0’ attribute object must be specified, which represents the baseline for the analysis and determines the attribute value(s) that can be selected for inclusion in the analysis. Depending on whether one or more items (attribute values) are selected, the results will provide insights on one item and its hotspots or allow for comparison of different items.
3. Third, the indicators to be considered in the hotspot analysis must be selected. These will be normalised and weighted to obtain a common base unit, based on the weighting factors/sets which also must be selected here (if several weighting sets are available, including an option of “equal weighting”). Here it is furthermore possible to unselect indicators or select just one, in which case the consecutive steps of the analysis will only consider the active indicators.
4. Fourth, the temporal attribute is defined, i.e., the attribute based on which the most relevant life cycle stages will be determined. The selection mask allows to select one or many life cycle stages, with all stages selected by default. Here it is possible to focus the analysis on selected life cycle stages, for example, to assess the most relevant indicators, life cycle stages and processes within the building use-phase, or for embodied impacts only.
5. Fifth, the ‘level -1’ attribute is specified, which represents the ‘process’ level in this analysis. The SLiCE tool is flexible with regards to defining ‘level-1’ as any spatial level below the initial ‘level0’ attribute. This means, for example, if ‘level0’ is the ‘building level’, then ‘level-1’ can be ‘building element’, ‘work section’, or ‘material level’, respectively.

6. Sixth, the threshold value for the cumulative impact of ‘most relevant’ items is defined. By default, it is set at 80%, as per the PEF/OEF hotspot analysis protocol, but can be changed as needed.
7. Lastly, when the above settings have been defined (or changed), pushing the ‘Run hotspot analysis’ button will run the analysis and generate (or updated) results tables and plots.

To prove the concept, a prototype of the SLiCE hotspots tool was developed (available with this article).

SLiCE – Hotspot Analysis Tool (Prototype)

Figure 8: Conceptual dashboard view of the SLiCE hotspot analysis tool prototype, showing elements of the user interface for relevant settings and examples of the generated results of the hotspot analysis, presented as tables and plots.

Figure 8 presents the original analyses and visualizations obtained from processing SLiCE data and confirms the feasibility of the concept. The data sample uses impact indicators and weighting sets of the Belgium MMG method [39–41], and has been tested with life cycle inventory data on building elements by [38] as well as SLiCE datasets of building level archetypes developed in the ‘Supporting a Roadmap for the Reduction of Whole Life Carbon in Buildings’ [43]. The detailed LCIA results were obtained through an implementation of the SLiCE data model within a comprehensive LCA modelling framework, building on the ‘MMG+_KULeuven’ model [39,42].

3.3. SLiCE-based dynamic LCA

One of the guiding design principles for developing the SLiCE data model was to provide high-resolution foreground inventory data for dynamic assessment of environmental impacts and potential carbon removals. The feasibility of the SLiCE data model for this purpose has been presented in [33].

3.3.1. Dynamic foreground LCI

The dynamic LCA builds on a SLiCE dataset of the respective building element, as illustrated by the example shown in Table 2, which provides a dynamic foreground LCI with explicit information on the type and timing of activities per year of the life cycle, i.e., a minimum spatial and temporal resolution of STI:D/-3. The SLiCE dataset includes a specification of the key spatial attributes: i.e., activity name (activity_name) and the related techflow (techflow_name), for soft linking to Ecoinvent background data. As well as information on temporal attributes: the life cycle stage (LCS_name) and timing of the activity (activity_year) and type of flow going in/out of the system (activity_type).

3.3.2. Static background LCI

The SLiCE dynamic foreground LCI is combined detailed static background LCI from Ecoinvent by mapping information based on the techflow name. In this example, the background LCI is only used to obtain data on the four main GHGs in relation to different life cycle stages specified in the foreground LCI, as illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3: Static LCI resulting from the combination of dynamic SLiCE foreground LCI and Ecoinvent background LCI, aggregated by life cycle stages given in the foreground LCI.

Life cycle stages	GHG emissions inventory			
	CO ₂ [kg]	CH ₄ [kg]	N ₂ O [kg]	CO [kg]
A1-A3	4.85E+01	8.03E-02	1.58E-03	1.86E-01
A4	2.40E+00	4.00E-03	7.77E-05	9.24E-03
B2	1.04E+00	2.03E-03	1.72E-05	4.04E-03
B4	2.22E+01	4.12E-02	1.42E-03	1.17E-01
C1, C3-4	4.51E+01	3.90E-03	1.97E-04	1.02E-02
Total	1.19E+02	1.32E-01	3.29E-03	3.27E-01

Background data on other biosphere flows could be used to dynamically assess other environmental impacts, such as, for example, land use or water scarcity. The present example utilizes a direct mapping of specific background and foreground LCI for providing further information on the specific GHG flows related to different activities in a certain year.

3.3.3. Static LCIA results

At first, a static LCIA is conducted to obtain reference results on the global warming potential (GWP) of the building element per square meter (m²) for a 100-year time horizon. The static LCIA results presented in Table 4 show that carbon dioxide (CO₂) has the largest contribution to the GWI, accounting for 96% of the total impact. Methane (CH₄) contributes 3%, while the remaining percentage is attributed to nitrous oxide (N₂O). The production phase has the greatest impact, representing 41.4% of the total, followed by the end-of-life phase with 36.5%, and replacements with 19.2%.

This approach is useful, as it utilizes the detailed LCI data to explicitly reveal the impact and contribution of different GHG to the total global warming impact of the product system, the case study building element. However, the static LCIA results still lack explicit information on the temporality of those emissions, crucial for understanding in which year they occur and what climate impact is associated with different pulse emissions over time.

Table 4: Static LCIA results for time horizon of 100 years.

Life cycle stages	GHG emissions impact				GWP
	kgCO ₂	kgCH ₄	kgN ₂ O	kgCO	[kgCO ₂ e]
A1-A3	4.85E+01	2.25E+00	4.18E-01	1.86E-01	5.13E+01
A4	2.40E+00	1.12E-01	2.06E-02	9.00E-03	2.54E+00
B2	1.04E+00	5.40E-02	4.54E-03	4.01E-03	1.10E+00
B4	2.22E+01	1.16E+00	3.76E-01	1.17E-01	2.38E+01
C1, C3-4	4.51E+01	1.09E-01	5.21E-02	1.00E-02	4.53E+01
Total	1.19E+02	3.68E+00	8.71E-01	3.26E-01	1.24E+02

3.3.4. Dynamic LCIA results

Figure 9: Illustration of dynamic life cycle assessment based on SLiCE showing (a) temporally explicit life cycle inventory (SLiCE) and (b) the resulting dynamic life cycle impact assessment graph. The graphs illustrate the GHG emission pulses (b) related to the activities occurring each year (a). As the specific types of activities in a given differ, so does the related GHG emissions 'pulse', which was computed using Ecoinvent background LCI data. The resulting dynamic climate impact (b) is therefore higher or lower, depending on the type of activity in the life cycle inventory.

The combination of a SLiCE-based dynamic foreground inventory and dynamic impact characterization factors allows this analysis of the temporal dynamics of climate impact. Figure 9 displays the dynamic impact of all considered GHGs, obtained by multiplying the LCI (bottom) with the corresponding

dynamic characterization factors (DCFs) to obtain dynamic LCIA results (bottom). The figure shows the dynamic climate impact results for CO₂ (blue), CH₄ (red), N₂O (green) and CO (purple). CO₂ emissions, as expected, have the largest contribution to dynamic climate impact results. Both CO₂ (blue) and CH₄ (red) show the highest peaks occurring during production and construction (year 0) and at the end-of-life (year 60) of the building element. Additional spikes can be seen at years 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50, mainly resulting from the replacement of nails, paint, and larch cladding. Notably, there are minimal emissions of N₂O (green) in the LCI. The patterns observed in the LCI graph (top) are reflected in the dynamic impact curves (bottom), with spikes at the beginning and end of the building element, as well as at intermediate years.

This presents the proof-of-concept for using SLiCE for dynamic life cycle impact assessment. The underlying thesis [33] applied this method to investigate dynamic climate impact as well as biogenic carbon uptake considering the effects of different scenarios regarding study time horizon, element service life, as well as forest rotation period and crediting of carbon uptake during harvest, i.e., from previous growth, or during regrowth. The methodology can further be developed to address existing limitations, such as the current cut-off after a predefined time horizon, which can be addressed by applying a ‘rolling time horizon’ (THr), which extends the study period by THr years beyond the year of the last activity/pulse. It is furthermore possible to distinguish the contribution to dynamic climate impact from different activities in the foreground inventory in a given year as well as cumulative across the time horizon.

3.4. Future development

Beyond the presented use cases of SLiCE data for high-granularity data and environmental hotspot analysis of buildings, various further use cases can be conceived in context of integrating LCA in building information modelling across spatiotemporal scales. In the following we present initial thoughts on functional, informational, organizational and technical aspects [44] to be further developed:

3.4.1. Functional aspects

Opportunity: Advanced analytics and visualization

This article focuses on accessible and high-resolution modelling of life cycle inventory (LCI) data and (environmental) life cycle indicator results obtained through comprehensive LCA. The STI logic and the SLiCE data model, however, are scalable and flexible regarding consideration of other indicators, such as, financial or social life cycle assessment, or specific aspects like circularity, criticality, or biodiversity impacts [45–50].

SLiCE datasets of a building's life cycle inventory and environmental indicators results offer a variety of opportunities for advanced analytics and visualization, which are yet to be fully explored. The presented use case of the data model for environmental hotspot analysis is only a first prototype which uses basic visualizations. Departing from the SLiCE data logic as a computational foundation, a variety of advanced visualization options can be developed for building LCA to ensure relevant insights are provided for different stakeholders and use cases, considering variabilities and uncertainty [51–55]

Challenge: Resource-intensive inventory modelling

Labour intensive modelling: While SLiCE support the handling of detailed LCI and LCIA data, the bottleneck of time-intensive definition of high-quality inventory data remains. Modular approaches as well as increased automation in life cycle inventory generation can help reduce the resource and labour intensity of this task [39,52,56]. In parallel to developing advanced analytics and visualization capabilities, the processes and workflows for LCI definition have to advance.

3.4.2. Informational aspects

Opportunity: Data enrichment and mappings

The SLiCE data structure and its computational backbone support the enrichment of a SLiCE dataset, for example by mapping onto it classifications from various building element classifications. Examples of such element classifications that can be mapped are national systems such as CI-SfB/BB-SfB [57], German DIN276, or Austrian ÖN1801, international industry standards such as UniClass, UniFormat, or transnational reporting requirements such as the Level(s) sustainability reporting framework [58,59]. A similar mapping is possible for information at the other scale levels contained in SLiCE data, such as mapping of material classification systems such as the Eurostat material accounts or conventions used

in studies relevant to a particular use case [60–62]. A comprehensive overview of systematic classification systems and the challenges and opportunities of using them in a building LCA context have been presented by [63].

The detailed information on a building's LCI and LCIA offered via SLiCE, can be combined with a detailed description of other attributes of the object of assessment, the building, such as attributes on the building's context and site, relevant building design characteristics, or variables related to assessment methods applied in a particular case study. A proposal for an extensive set of attributes for building description in context of benchmarking whole life carbon is presented in [30].

Challenge: Input data availability and granularity

A challenge yet unsolved is the availability and granularity of input data relevant to informing the life cycle modelling of buildings and building stocks. Detailed information on the micro-level, such as the composition of building elements, can often be obtained through reviewing technical documentations or, if needed, surveying on-site (see labour intensive modelling bottleneck). Detailed information on the macro-level, however, is currently limited to statistical data on the regional material and energy flows obtained from multi-regional input-output (MRIO) models. While certainly useful for many applications, the data provided by such models mostly lacks the necessary granularity when it comes to buildings, for which it would be relevant to understand resource flows not just between regions, but between different types of buildings and activities (How much concrete is used for the new construction of single-family houses in a given year?). Extended definition and use of data reporting standards for information relevant to life cycle modelling of both buildings and stocks can hopefully improve this situation in the future. The advancement of corporate sustainability reporting standards, as well as the revamp of platforms such as the Building Stock Observatory [64] as well as other data collection efforts such as the BuiltHub project [65], offer glimpses of what next steps might look like.

3.4.3. Organizational aspects

Opportunity: Digital Building Logbooks

The SLiCE data model is agnostic with regards to the use of prospective, scenario-based information, or information based on as-built or in-use measurements. In practice, a SLiCE dataset could hence be used in a first steps to store both, the initial life cycle assessment results, based on plausible life cycle scenarios. In a second step, and through iterations at various points across the use phase, the initial life cycle data can be replaced with as-built or in-use measurements to represent the actual building condition and performance and update the SLiCE dataset accordingly. In that regard, a SLiCE dataset, storing detailed information on the building life cycle inventory and related environmental impacts, can be one of several modules and an integral part of a digital building logbook or digital twins more broadly [66–69].

Challenge: Stakeholder-specific needs

As different stakeholders have different needs, the features of SLiCE data model and its implementation in different tools will evolve over time. As of today, the SLiCE data model has been developed from a building LCA perspective and the use of high granularity building data within high resolution models of building stock up to macro-scale. The link between building and building stock level is particularly important to support detailed life cycle modelling for testing the effects of building-level decarbonization strategies when upscaled to the macro-level. Data models such as SLiCE are important for ensuring a robust link between building and building stock level that can avoid unnecessary loss of data through aggregation or computational inefficiencies.

3.4.4. Technical aspects

Opportunity: Dynamic impact assessment

The detailed life cycle inventory offered by SLiCE data, if including a specification of flows and processes by ‘point in time’ (e.g., per year), can further be the basis for modelling dynamic impact characterization, such as for temporally dynamic assessment of climate impacts. A proof-of-concept of such a dynamic characterisation of climate impact in context of bio-based construction materials has been presented by [33]. Detailed life cycle inventory data provided using the SLiCE data model can furthermore include the specification of related background LCA datasets (e.g., reference to datasets in the Ecoinvent database), in order to enable spatially dynamic assessment, i.e., regionalization of the

background data as well as the impact assessment, for example via tools like Brightway [70–73]). Furthermore, the life cycle assessment implications from potential future dynamics in technological innovation [74] can be assessed that way.

Opportunity: High resolution LCA modelling at higher scales

Finally, the potential of SLiCE data to handle high granularity LCI and LCIA in an efficient way, can enable increased model resolution in life cycle assessment at higher scale levels, such as for environmental modelling of building stocks at macro-scale. The modelling of higher scales, beyond the buildings level, can be expected to follow different logics as the building LCA life cycle information model, the ability to map the detailed LCI and LCIA data offered by SLiCE with definitions common in building stock modelling will be useful. SLiCE results per life cycle stage can, for example, be mapped with different building stock level activities, such as new building construction (considering results in life cycle stages A1 to A5), to obtain insights into the upfront impacts or emissions of such activities from a bottom-up perspective.

4. Conclusion

This article and model respond to the need of policy and decision makers to understand (environmental) hotspots along the life cycle of buildings. In this article we present the SLiCE building data model as a basis for scalable life cycle engineering and analysis of buildings across spatiotemporal dimensions.

The hitherto unresolved challenge of providing and processing high granularity building life cycle information to support the needs of policy and decision makers is conceptualised within the proposed space-time-indicator (STI) framework. The STI framework serves as a means of communicating the availability and requirements for building life cycle information regarding diverse indicators at different levels of granularity along spatial and temporal dimensions. Subsequently, the SLiCE data model is introduced, and its data structure explained. Furthermore, relevant example use cases are presented by implementing SLiCE-based systematic protocol for the analysis of (environmental) hotspots within building life cycle information. The proof-of-concept for using SLiCE data for hotspot analysis data model is implemented within a functional model for hotspot analysis. Furthermore, an exemplary use

case of SLiCE for dynamic LCA is presented based on the combination of dynamic LCI data from SLiCE. Both applications are implemented via IPython Jupyter Notebooks with interactive UI elements.

The SLiCE data model, the SLiCE hotspot analysis prototype, as well as the SLiCE-based dynamic impact assessment logic are henceforth available for implementation within future building LCA workflows and tools for high-definition life cycle assessment of buildings and building stocks.

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